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Opto-mechanical analogue of Peierls transition

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E-mail: seib@mci.sdu.dk**Keywords:** Peierls transition, grating waveguide couplers, optical forces**Abstract**

Peierls transition is associated with a metal-insulator transition due to a displacive distortion in a regular quasi one-dimensional ion array that increases the unit cell length, creating a band gap in the electronic band structure. Here, we introduce the opto-mechanical analogue of Peierls transition that occurs in diffraction grating waveguide couplers, operating at normal light incidence, with grating ridges being able to move along the waveguide surface. We analyze optical gradient forces acting on slightly displaced grating ridges, i.e. making double the grating period and enabling resonant excitation of waveguide modes at the wavelength of their Bragg reflection produced by an unperturbed grating, thus strongly influencing the light transmission. We identify the wavelength ranges, within which the optical forces move further grating ridges to certain positions, at which the net force along the waveguide plane becomes zero, resulting in the stable asymmetric grating and strongly suppressed light transmission. Possible realizations of this transition are discussed, including the potential realization of all-optical dynamic nanophotonic components based on grating configurations with mechanical restoring forces.

1. Introduction

About 90 years ago [1], Peierls discovered that a one-dimensional (1D) equally spaced ion chain with one electron per ion (i.e. 1D metal), is unstable against a periodic lattice distortion (typically doubling the lattice period) that would open a band gap (BG) at the Fermi energy [2]. The periodic lattice deformation (also known as the Peierls distortion) results in lowering the filled one-electron energy states, which outweighs the cost in strain energy thus making the deformed state stable [3]. At sufficiently low temperatures, the deformed state would correspond to an insulator, so that a metal at high temperatures would transform into an insulator at low temperatures in the first-order phase transition termed as the Peierls metal-insulator transition [4]. The Peierls transition in general has been found responsible for various physical phenomena observed in low-dimensional electronic crystals [3], including metallization of vanadium dioxide [5] and interlayer decoupling in semiconductor transition metal dichalcogenides [6].

Analogy between the descriptions of trajectories in classical mechanics and wave propagation (Hamiltonian analogy) has motivated establishing analogies between quantum mechanics and optics [7]. Following these developments, many concepts in quantum mechanics and solid-state physics have been advantageously exploited in modern optics and photonics, including waveguide optics, photonic crystals and topological photonics. Bearing in mind the Peierls distortion, we started considering the transmission of electromagnetic waves through structurally perturbed systems [8]. Engineered optical systems, such as synthetic photonic lattices or periodically corrugated integrated optical waveguides, can be designed to mimic perturbed electron potential considered in the Peierls distortion.

The analogy to the Peierls transition becomes particularly compelling when one considers that light propagating through a perfectly periodic 1D structure can be described using a band structure analogous to the electronic band structure in a 1D ion chain, i.e. featuring the BG at the wavelength that is twice larger than the periodicity [9]. In the BG vicinity, one finds counter propagating waveguide modes

coupled by Bragg reflection, i.e. forming the distributed Bragg resonator (DBR) that has intensively been investigated in the context of semiconductor lasers [10].

In the spirit of Peierls transition, we consider waveguide grating ridges being free to move along the waveguide plane (like ions being displaced along a 1D chain in the Peierls transition). If every second grating ridge would spontaneously (and equally) be displaced, the waveguide grating would become asymmetric featuring the double period as compared to the unperturbed grating. The main consequence would be the possibility for normally incident radiation at the BG wavelength to efficiently excite the counter-propagating waveguide modes that are coupled by the DBR, resulting in strongly modified transmission [11]. The overall effect would then be the attenuation of light transmission by displacing grating ridges, a phenomenon that is similar to the attenuation of the electron transport in Peierls transition. For the analogy to Peierls transition to be justified, there should be physical effects causing ridge displacements, with the optical forces acting on illuminated objects to appear as a natural candidate. Recent advances in integrated opto-mechanics [12] open wide possibilities for exploiting optically induced mechanical forces and associated distortions of photonic configurations.

Bearing in mind the above considerations, we turn now our attention to the interplay between optical transmission of normally incident radiation and light-induced displacements of waveguide grating ridges, which are assumed to be freely moving along the waveguide plane thus transforming a symmetric grating into an asymmetric one with the double period. The wavelength range of interest is near the BG of waveguide modes formed by Bragg reflection in an unperturbed symmetric waveguide grating, a range that also allows for the excitation of waveguide modes by a distorted asymmetric grating with the double period [10], i.e. $\lambda/N_{\text{ef}} \cong \Lambda_s/2 = \Lambda_{\text{as}}$ (N_{ef} is the effective mode index, Λ_s and Λ_{as} are the periods of symmetric and asymmetric gratings, respectively). Note that, for the normal light incidence on symmetric gratings, the net optical force acting on grating ridges along the waveguide plane is zero because of the mirror symmetry of configuration, while it is expected to become nonzero for asymmetric waveguide gratings. The dynamic interplay between the optical field distribution established in the waveguide due to its excitation and the optically induced grating distortion responsible for the waveguide excitation and transmission modification opens a pathway to light-induced Peierls-like instabilities.

In this work, we present a theoretical framework and numerical simulations establishing the conditions under which spontaneous ridge displacements, i.e. distortions of a symmetric grating, result in nonzero net optical force acting on grating ridges along the waveguide plane as well as in resonant waveguide excitation and thereby strongly attenuated light transmission, a phenomenon that we attribute to opto-mechanical Peierls transition. We analyze light-induced forces and mechanical instabilities, establish conditions allowing for instability onset, and discuss light-induced transmission spectrum variations. Our results point to new mechanisms for all-optical tunability in photonic BG structures and their optical characteristics, i.e. for light-controlled optical phase transitions in engineered waveguide systems.

2. General configuration

The waveguide grating configuration under consideration (figure 1(a)) is identical with that analyzed in our previous studies of quasi-bound states in the continuum (qBIC) in asymmetric waveguide gratings [11] and associated finite-size effects [13]. In this work, we concentrate on the fundamental waveguide mode that can be excited at ~ 1900 nm with 1200 nm-period gratings [11]. Consequently, the unperturbed symmetric grating considered here has a period of 600 nm (figure 1(b)), and no waveguide modes can be excited with this grating at normal incidence of telecom wavelengths. In accordance with the above reasoning, we now assume that the grating ridges can freely move along the waveguide surface. This assumption allows us to focus on the underlying physical processes, while a realistic implementation of such a system is discussed in detail later, in the concluding part of our paper. We further consider a spontaneous displacement of paired ridges towards each other (figures 1(c) and (d)), producing thereby an asymmetric 1200 nm-period grating that enables the first-order excitation of the fundamental waveguide mode resulting in the attenuated transmission (figure 1(e)).

Similar situation, albeit with the distortion introduced by slightly changing the width of every second grating ridge, was thoroughly investigated in our recent work, where the focus was on the occurrence of qBIC and BIC resonances under a plane-wave normal incidence [11]. The operation principle is, however, similar in both cases: the waveguide mode excitation occurs in the first diffraction order of distorted asymmetric grating at the same wavelength, at which the DBR condition is satisfied with the unperturbed symmetric grating. For small distortion, the period of the latter is exactly equal to the period of a second-order grating produced by the asymmetric grating as noted [10]. In brief, the mode excitation occurs due to a weak grating asymmetry and therefore vanishes for vanishing asymmetry. At the same

time, the DBR is formed by a strong unperturbed grating and only weakly perturbed by asymmetry [11]. This combination results in narrow transmission minima associated with qBIC resonance, whose spectral width is inversely proportional to the square of perturbation [11, 14], transmission minima that are also very deep even for very small distortions (figure 1).

Note that all reported in this work simulations were performed with commercial software comsol multiphysics based on finite-element-method (the typical mesh size was set to 50 nm, however being finer inside the grating ridges). Floquet periodic conditions were used on the boundaries of the unit cell (2D, i.e. the structure is infinite along the grating ridges) with a width of 1200 nm (containing two ridges). A 1.2 μm -thin film of Al_2O_3 on a 500 μm -thick MgF_2 substrate serves as a waveguide, while the grating is formed by 50 nm-high and 150 nm-wide germanium ridges. For the permittivity of Al_2O_3 , MgF_2 we used interpolated values [15, 16].

The real part of the permittivity of Ge with the account of dispersion was taken from [17], however the imaginary part was approximated as constant and set to 0.01, to minimize computational complexity. The incident field is transverse electric (TE), i.e. polarized along the grating ridges. Further, to minimize the effect of mesh on the outcome, we move the two ridges in the unit cell towards each other simultaneously (figure 1), hence the symmetry in the simulation domain is conserved when the distortion is introduced, with the ridge-to-ridge separation being modified by 2δ .

Hereafter we consider the optical transmission spectra and those of the optical net force acting on the grating ridges along the waveguide plane. The transmission spectra simulations are conducted similarly to those previously reported [11], while the force calculation requires more explanations. Optical forces acting on the grating ridges can conveniently be computed by making use of Maxwell's stress tensor formalism [18]. The latter allows one to calculate the optical force acting on an object enclosed within a surface V as follows:

$$\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle = \int_S \langle \overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \rangle \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r}) da, \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the time average, $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{r})$ is the normal to the surface of the volume V , S is the surface enclosing the volume V and $\overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the so-called Maxwell's stress tensor, which is defined as follows:

$$\overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_0 \left(E_x^2 - \frac{E^2}{2} \right) + \mu_0 \left(H_x^2 - \frac{H^2}{2} \right) & \varepsilon_0 E_x E_y + \mu_0 H_x H_y & \varepsilon_0 E_x E_z + \mu_0 H_x H_z \\ \varepsilon_0 E_x E_y + \mu_0 H_x H_y & \varepsilon_0 \left(E_y^2 - \frac{E^2}{2} \right) + \mu_0 \left(H_y^2 - \frac{H^2}{2} \right) & \varepsilon_0 E_y E_z + \mu_0 H_y H_z \\ \varepsilon_0 E_x E_z + \mu_0 H_x H_z & \varepsilon_0 E_y E_z + \mu_0 H_y H_z & \varepsilon_0 \left(E_z^2 - \frac{E^2}{2} \right) + \mu_0 \left(H_z^2 - \frac{H^2}{2} \right) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

In the above expression, E and H represent the corresponding electric and magnetic field components, respectively. Since we are interested in lateral movements we will calculate only the x -component of the optical forces (figure 2(a)). The right ridge in the supercell with the corresponding forces acting on it is considered further, using the following simplified expressions extracted from equations (1) and (2):

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_R &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{sR} \left(-\varepsilon_0 E_z^2 + \mu_0 H_x^2 - \mu_0 H_y^2 \right) da \\
 F_L &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{sL} \left(\varepsilon_0 E_z^2 - \mu_0 H_x^2 + \mu_0 H_y^2 \right) da \\
 F_T &= \int_{sT} \mu_0 H_x H_y da \\
 F_B &= - \int_{sB} \mu_0 H_x H_y da
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

with the indices R , L , T , and B denoting forces acting on the right, left, top and bottom edges, respectively (figure 2(a)). And the total force acting laterally is the sum of these four: $F_t = F_R + F_L + F_T + F_B$. Note that the employed approach for calculating the optical force (equation (1)) is formulated for an isolated particle [18]. However, in the considered system, the incident field has only a tangential component, which is conserved. Therefore, introducing a vanishingly small air gap between the Ge ridges and the waveguiding substrate would not change the electromagnetic field distributions, allowing for the calculations of optical forces with the above equations (equation (3)).

3. Simulation results

The optical transmission and net force spectra are calculated for very small ridge displacements (figure 2) to understand the system evolution starting from spontaneous ridge displacements as discussed in the introduction. It is seen that the optical transmission spectra demonstrate the occurrence

and expected tendency of increasing and broadening the transmission minimum for ridges being displaced further away from their original positions in the symmetric grating (figure 2(b)).

Moreover, the transmission spectra at normal incidence indicate that even small variations in the ridge positions lead to substantial changes in transmission, so that already at the ridge displacement of $\delta = 2$ nm the transmission drops by $\sim 20\%$ at resonance (figure 2(b)), while $\delta = 10$ nm results in almost fully suppressed transmitted light. The influence of displacement δ on the transmission spectra is twofold: (i) the in/out-coupling efficiency of the asymmetric grating is proportional to δ (for small δ), because this displacement is responsible for the formation of this double-period grating in the first place, and (ii) the transmission minimum, approaching to zero for larger δ , moves to longer wavelengths with δ (figure 1(e)), because the phase of outcoupled radiation and thus the interference of the outcoupled and directly transmitted radiation depend on δ .

Further, to understand the dynamics of the system we calculate optical forces acting on grating ridges. Optical forces are proportional to the incident field intensity (equation (3)) that is arbitrarily chosen as being equal to 83 mW cm^{-2} for the presented simulations. It should be borne in mind that the initial (spontaneous) displacement is introduced by slightly moving the right ridge in the unit cell towards the negative direction of the x -axis. Hence, the positive optical net force, i.e. directed towards the positive direction of the x -axis, is restoring the symmetric configuration, while the negative force is disturbing, i.e. increasing the grating asymmetry. The calculated force spectra reveal that, even for displacements as small as 1 nm, the force spectra exhibit both positive and negative values, depending on the wavelength (figure 2(c)).

This is an extremely important feature in the context of our study, as it signifies the possibility of spontaneously occurred ridge displacements to ‘survive’ and even result in further evolution of the grating away from the symmetric configuration, if the incident light wavelength is appropriately chosen. Even though the theoretical framework used in this work does not allow us to analyze directly dynamics of ridge displacements, we can still deduce that the points of zero net force marked in figure 2(b) are related to the stable configurations, i.e. slight ridge displacements from the considered positions would result in the forces moving ridges back to their original displaced positions. This stability is the consequence of the interplay between two important features in the force spectra (figure 2(c)): wavelengths corresponding to zero net forces are larger for larger displacements, and the restoring forces correspond to shorter wavelengths. The existence of stable configurations is a very nontrivial and important feature in the considered phenomenon, making it promising for eventual experimental observation and potential exploitation for realizing all-optical dynamic metasurfaces.

It is instructive to make the back-of-the-envelope estimation of the optical force magnitude. In doing so, we assume that the main contribution to the net force (figure 2(c)) comes from the asymmetry, α , in the contribution from the field term, H_y^2 , generated by the excited TE waveguide mode, which is also enhanced by coupling to the counterpropagating one in the DBR. Assuming further that the mode field (average) intensity is enhanced in comparison with that of the incident wave (I_0) by the enhancement factor Γ , the net force can be estimated as follows:

$$F \sim \alpha \Gamma I_0 \frac{hL}{c}, \quad (4)$$

where c is the speed of light, h and L are the height and length of the grating ridge. In the limit of large asymmetry, $\alpha \sim 1$, and assuming that at the resonance $\Gamma \sim Q$ —the quality factor of the DBR ($Q \sim 10^5$ in our case), one obtains with equation (4) the following force estimate: $F \sim 1.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ N m}^{-1}$, which is of the same order as in our numerical calculations (figure 2(c)). Even though the obtained estimation, equation (4), is very approximate, it does serve the purpose of highlighting the essential trends, that are also consistent with our simulations (figure 2(c)): the force is generally larger for larger displacements δ , resulting in larger asymmetry α in electromagnetic field distribution. We have also found that the distorting force is smaller for more absorptive (e.g. with larger absorption in Ge ridges) systems, i.e. with lower resonance quality factors. Finally, the distorting forces reach maximum values at wavelengths that are close to the corresponding transmission minima, where the stored in DBR fields are maximized.

To further deepen the insight into the system dynamics, we consider the transmission and force dependences on the ridge displacement δ corresponding to a set of specific wavelengths, as the latter are assumed to be constant during the optically induced system evolution (figure 3). It is immediately seen that, depending on the light wavelength, one observes two distinctly different regimes in the system dynamics: one with the force being always positive (i.e. restoring) and another regime with the force changing from negative (distorting) to positive values (figure 3(a)).

Indeed, in the wavelength range of 1881.8–1881.84 nm, the optical net force acting along the waveguide surface is always positive for all ridge displacements larger than 1 nm, thus pushing the displaced

Figure 3. Optical force (a) and transmission (b) dependences on the ridge displacement δ calculated for different wavelengths, with the crosses indicating the zero-force ridge displacements.

Figure 4. Forces acting on each edge of the ridge illuminated at the wavelength of 1881.86 nm for different distortions of the ridge position (a). Stress and torque on the right ridge in a supercell as a function of distortion (b).

ridges back to the unperturbed positions of the symmetric grating. The situation changes drastically for longer wavelengths in the range of 1881.85–1881.9 nm, for which even very small displacements down to 1 nm result in negative optical forces that push the displaced ridges further away from the unperturbed positions (figure 3(a)). For these wavelengths, tiny spontaneous ridge displacements would eventually result (in the absence of mechanical friction) in the equilibrium displacements corresponding to zero net forces, i.e. in reaching the stable asymmetric waveguide gratings. Importantly, the light transmission by these stable configurations is strongly attenuated compared to that by the unperturbed symmetric grating configuration figure 3(b). Therefore, for specific wavelengths, the spontaneous transition from high to low light transmission is expected to occur as a consequence of spontaneously initiated ridge displacements resulting in stable asymmetric grating configurations, the transition that overall is rather similar in spirit to the attenuation of the electron transport in Peierls transition.

It is also instructive to consider different contributions to the net force acting on the ridge. It turns out that the largest forces are indeed (as assumed in our above force estimation) those acting on the left and right ridge sides (figure 4(a)) and oriented in opposite directions, trying to stretch the ridge, i.e. to increase its width.

The forces acting on the top and bottom ridge sides are also opposite to each other as expected from the formulas in equation (3), impairing thereby the torque on the ridge. Both optically induced

stress and torque pick up at the displacement that results in the minimum transmission (cf figures 4(b) and 3(b)), reflecting the fact that the optical forces are related to the squared magnitudes of electromagnetic field components that are enhanced at resonance. Note that the stress and torque are not expected, even at their maximum, to result in noticeable modifications of the configuration (e.g. the optically induced deformation in Ge ridges is estimated to be $\sim 10^{-9}$ nm).

The situation with the net displacing force is quite different: the force of $\sim 10^{-8}$ N m $^{-1}$ would move the considered (50×150 nm 2) ridge made of Ge from the rest position by 10 nm in ~ 9 μ s, i.e. quite fast. The acting force can also be easily increased by increasing the incident light intensity, as 83 mW cm $^{-2}$ (used on our calculations) is a rather low intensity as far as typical optical experiments are concerned. Finally, it is worth noting that the stable configurations (marked by crosses in figure 3(b)) correspond to transmissions that are not at the minimum levels. It is also seen that the optimum, from the viewpoint of obtaining the smallest transmission at the stable configuration, wavelength is found different from that ensuring the deepest transmission minimum (figure 3(b)).

4. Conclusions

In this communication, we introduced the opto-mechanical analogue of Peierls transition that occurs in diffraction grating waveguide couplers, operating at normal light incidence, with grating ridges being able to move along the waveguide surface. We analyzed optical gradient forces acting on slightly displaced grating ridges, i.e. making double the grating period and enabling resonant excitation of waveguide modes at the wavelength of their Bragg reflection produced by an unperturbed grating, thus strongly influencing the light transmission. We identified the wavelength ranges, within which the optical forces move further grating ridges to certain positions, at which the net force along the waveguide plane becomes zero, resulting in stable asymmetric grating and strongly suppressed light transmission.

The salient features of the considered phenomenon are general and can be implemented with different materials and in various wavelength ranges—it would suffice to choose the waveguide and grating geometry. Consequently, there can be considered various possible realizations of this transition. The grating ridges do not have to be completely free to move. One could place ridges on a nm-thin polymer layer, e.g. made of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), supported by the waveguide configuration. Designing the ridge configuration with a small displacement of every second ridge, i.e. being asymmetric from the very beginning, would open the possibility of stretching the polymer layer by optically induced forces and thereby changing the light transmission (and reflection) accordingly. In this case, the stable ridge positions would occur at the balance between distorting optical and restoring (from the stretched polymer) forces, implying the possibility to adjust the incident light intensity so that the minimum transmission is realized. Indeed, considering the Young's modulus of PDMS as ~ 100 kPa [19], the PDMS thickness ~ 100 nm, and the grating period ~ 1 μ m, one finds that the force of 10^{-4} N m $^{-1}$ is required to move the ridge by 10 nm. In our system (figure 2(c)), the optically induced force of that size will be generated with $a \sim 20$ mW laser beam illuminating 100×100 μ m 2 , which is a typical size of optical metasurfaces used in practice.

The above estimations indicate rich possibilities provided by the considered phenomenon for realizing all-optical dynamic nanophotonic components based on grating configurations with mechanical restoring forces. Dispensing with the necessity of relying on spontaneous and synchronous ridge displacements by using an introduced grating asymmetry, broadens potential applications considerably, suggesting applications as all-optical switches and logical gates.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article with any supplementary materials being available from the corresponding author upon request.

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